

**PHARMACOGNOSTICAL AND PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS OF
LASHUNADI TAILA - AN AYURVEDIC HERBAL FORMULATION FOR
VANDHYATVA (FEMALE INFERTILITY) DUE TO ANOVULATORY
FACTOR ASSOCIATED WITH OBESITY**

Alifeeya Vaghela¹, Shilpa B. Donga², Harisha C. R.³

¹PG Scholar, Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stree Roga,

²Prof. & H.O.D., Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stree Roga,

³Pharmacognosy Laboratory, Institute of Teaching and Research in Ayurveda (ITRA), Opp.

B Division Police Station, Near Reliance Mall, Gurudwara road Jamnagar, Gujarat, India-

361008.

Article Received on 05 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 25 Jan. 2026,
Article Published on 01 Feb. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18480153>

***Corresponding Author**

Alifeeya Vaghela

PG Scholar, Department of Prasuti
Tantra Evam Stree Roga.

How to cite this Article: Alifeeya Vaghela¹, Shilpa B. Donga², Harisha C. R.³. (2026). Pharmacognostical and Pharmaceutical Analysis of Lashunadi Taila - An Ayurvedic Herbal Formulation For Vandhyatva (Female Infertility) Due To Anovulatory Factor Associated With Obesity. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(3), 1551-1550. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Background: Infertility is a major global health concern affecting nearly 10–15% of reproductive-age couples. According to Ayurveda, infertility (*Vandhyatva*) is primarily caused by vitiation of *Vata*, and classical texts emphasize the profound physical and psychosocial impact of childlessness. Acharya Kashyapa specifically recommends *Lashunadi Taila* for the management of *Vandhyatva* mentioned as *Veerya-praja-pradam*. This formulation comprises 36 drugs, including *Lashuna* (*Allium sativum* L.) as the prime ingredient, along with *Deepaniya*, *Vrishya*, *Jeevaniya Gana*, and *Dashamoola*, making it therapeutically significant in gynecological disorders. So, for initialization of standardization and assurance of the quality of herbal compounds, pharmacognostical and pharmaceutical analysis should be done. **Methods:** *Lashunadi Taila* was subjected to microscopic evaluation for pharmacognostical and physicochemical analysis such as acid

value, Specific gravity, Saponification value and Iodine value. **Results:** Pharmacognostical study showed the presence of certain identifying characters of all the ingredients of *Lashunadi Taila* like *Lashuna*, *Dravyas* of *Deepaniya*, *Mahakashaya*, *Jeevaniya*

Mahakashaya, Vrishya Dravyas and Dashamoola Dravyas. As per the preliminary physico-chemical analysis, Acid value of the *Lashunadi Taila* was 12.04, Specific gravity value was 0.91, Saponification value was 386.46 and Iodine value was 649.13. **Conclusions:** Pharmacognostical and physico-chemical observations revealed the specific characteristics of all active constituents of *Lashunadi Taila* confirmed the purity and genuineness of the drug.

KEYWORDS: *Lashunadi Taila, Vandhyatva, Pharmacognosy, Pharmaceutical analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

Infertility is a global health issue that affects millions of couples and can have significant emotional, psychological, and social impacts. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines infertility as ‘A disease of the reproductive system defined by the failure to achieve a clinical pregnancy after 12 months or more of regular unprotected sexual intercourse.’^[1] And patients aged 35 years or more completed active married life of six months with regular unprotected sexual intercourse.^[2] It affects 10–15% of reproductive-age couples globally, with up to 48 million women affected worldwide.^[3] As per the WHO data, around 17.5% of the adult population – roughly 1 in 6 worldwide – experience infertility.^[4] In India, 3.9 to 16.8% of females suffer from primary infertility.^[5] According to Ayurveda, infertility, or *Vandhyatva*, is one of 80 ailments brought on by the vitiation of *Vata*.^[6] Infertile couples were seen as shadeless by Acharya Charaka as branchless, fruitless was tree that doesn't provide any light or brightness, similar to a lamp in a painting or portrait. After conception and childbirth, the goal of womanhood is fulfilled. For *Vandhya*, Acharya Kashyapa has recommended *Lashunadi Taila*.^[7]

Lashunadi Taila contains total 36 drugs which are commonly used in gynecological disorders. Acharya Kashyapa has mentioned *Deepaniya, Vrishya, Jeevaniya Gana* and *Dashamoola* add it in for preparation. Prime ingredient of *Lashunadi Taila* is *Lashuna (Allium sativum L.)*. Herbal medications must be safe, effective, free of adulteration, and have the proper dose and ingredients when taken internally. It can be difficult to identify herbal medications when they are dry or powdered. Consequently, suitable standards for the standardization of herbal medicines must be established. In the case of herbal traditional medicine, pharmacognocical research identify plants and establish standards for standardization. Generally speaking, physiochemical analysis can be used to assess the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of drugs. Physiochemical analytical studies can help standardize the drug and distinguish adulterants. Time is of the essence in the field of

Ayurveda in order to guarantee the high quality of the raw medications. The field of Ayurveda must strive for quality control of both raw and finished drugs using modern standards in order to legitimize Ayurvedic medicines and support their globalization. Thus, the goal of the current study was to develop *Lashunadi Taila's* pharmacognostical and phytochemical profile and evaluate its authenticity by a range of pharmacognostical procedures.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Collection, identification and authentication of raw drugs.

The raw materials were procured from the pharmacy of ITRA Jamnagar, authentic source and the raw drugs were identified and authenticated in the pharmacognosy laboratory of ITRA, Ministry of Ayush, Gov. of India, Jamnagar. The ingredients and part used of *Lashunadi Taila* are given in Table 1.

Table No. 1: Ingredients Of *Lashunadi Taila*.

Drug Name	Botanical name	Family	Part Used	Proportion
<i>Lashuna</i>	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Liliaceae	Rhizome	100 Pala
<i>Tila Taila</i>	<i>Sesamum indicum</i> Linn.	Pedaliaceae	Seed	1 <i>Adhaka</i>
<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Piper longum</i> Linn.	Piperaceae	Fruit	12 gm
<i>Pippali Moola</i>	<i>Piper longum</i> Linn.	Piperaceae	Root	12 gm
<i>Chavya</i>	<i>Piper chaba</i> D.C.	Piperaceae	Fruit	12 gm
<i>Chitraka</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> Linn.	Plumbaginaceae	Root Bark	12 gm
<i>Shringavera</i>	<i>Zingiber officinalis</i> Roscoe.	Scitamineceae	Rhizome	12 gm
<i>Amlavetasa</i>	<i>Garcinia pedunculata</i> Roxb.	Cucurbitaceae	Root	12 gm
<i>Maricha</i>	<i>Piper nigrum</i> Linn.	Piperaceae	Fruit	12 gm
<i>Ajamoda</i>	<i>Apium graveolens</i> Linn.	Umbeliferaea	Fruit	12 gm
<i>Bhallatakasthi</i>	<i>Semicarpus anacardium</i> Linn.	Anacardaceae	Fruit	12 gm
<i>Hinguniryasa</i>	<i>Ferula narthex</i> Regel.	Apiaceae	Extract	12 gm
<i>Jivaka-Rishabhaka= Vidari</i>	<i>Pueraria tuberosa</i> (Roxb.ex.Wild) D.C.	Leguminosae	Tuber	24 gm
<i>Meda-Mahamda= Shatavari</i>	<i>Asparagus Racemosus</i> Wild.	Liliaceae	Root	24 gm
<i>Kakoli-Ksheerakakoli-Aswagandha</i>	<i>Withania somnifera</i> Dunal.	Solanaceae	Root	24 gm
<i>Mudgaparni</i>	<i>Phaseolus trilobus</i> Ait.	Leguminosae	Whole Plant	12 gm
<i>Mashaparni</i>	<i>Teramnus labialis</i> Spreng.	Leguminosae	Whole Plant	12 gm

<i>Jivanti</i>	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i> W&A	Asclepiadaceae	Stem	12 gm
<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> Linn.	Leguminosae	Root	12 gm
<i>Kapikachchhu</i>	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> Bek.	Leguminosae	Seed	12 gm
<i>Atibala</i>	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> Linn.	Malvaceae	Root	12 gm
<i>Krishna Musali</i>	<i>Curculigo orchioides</i> Gaertn.	Liliaceae	Root	12 gm
<i>Sweta Musali</i>	<i>Chlorophytum arundinaceum</i> Baker.	Liliaceae	Root	12 gm
<i>Ikshuraka</i>	<i>Astercanthas longifolia</i> Linn.	Acantheceae	Whole Plant	12 gm
<i>Karkatashringi</i>	<i>Pistacia intergerrima</i> Stew.	Anacardiaceae	Insect Galls	12 gm
<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Embelica officinalis</i> Linn.	Euphorbiaceae	Fruit	12 gm
<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Roxb.	Combratraceae	Fruit	12 gm
<i>Bilva</i>	<i>Aegle marmelous</i> Corr.	Rutaceae	Root/ Stem bark	12 gm
<i>Gambhari</i>	<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Linn.	Verbenaceae	Root/ Stem bark	12 gm
<i>Patala</i>	<i>Stereospermum suaveolens</i> DC.	Bignoniaceae	Root/ Stem bark	12 gm
<i>Agnimantha</i>	<i>Clerodendrum phlomidis</i> Linn.	Verbenaceae	Root/ Stem bark	12 gm
<i>Shyonaka</i>	<i>Oroxylum indicum</i> Vent.	Bignoniaceae	Root/ Stem bark	12 gm
<i>Shalaparni</i>	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> DC.	Solanaceae	Whole Plant	12 gm
<i>Prishniparni</i>	<i>Uraria picta</i> Desv.	Solanaceae	Whole Plant	12 gm
<i>Brihati</i>	<i>Solanum indicum</i> Linn.	Solanaceae	Whole Plant	12 gm
<i>Kantakari</i>	<i>Solanum xanthocarpum</i> Sachrad & Wendl	Solanaceae	Whole Plant	12 gm
<i>Gokshura</i>	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> Linn.	Zygophyllaceae	Fruit	12 gm

METHOD OF PREPARATION OF LASHUNADI TAILA

Firstly, sesame oil was taken in a vessel, then it was subjected for heating procedure. After moisture free stage of the vessel, *Sneha*, *Kalka* and *Drava* indicated in *Lashunadi Taila Paka Vidhi* were added in the specified quantity. Heat was given continuously till *Taila Paka Siddhi Lakshanas* were attained, then it was filtered through cotton cloth. After self-cooling, it was stored in air tight bottle.

PHARMACOGNOSTICAL STUDY

The pharmacognostical study was divided into organoleptic study and microscopic study of the finished product.

Organoleptic study: The genuineness of the polyherbal formulation can be found with organoleptic characters of the given sample. Organoleptic parameters comprise of colour, odour, taste and touch of *Lashunadi Taila*, which was scientifically studied.

Microscopic study: Ingredients of *Lashunadi Taila* were taken in powder form and dissolved with water and microscopy of the sample was done without stain and after staining with phloroglucinol and HCl. Microphotographs of all ingredients of *Lashunadi Taila* were also taken under Carl-zeiss trinocular microscope.^[8]

Physico-chemical analysis: With the help of various standard physico-chemical parameters, *Lashunadi Taila* was analysed. The common parameters mentioned for *Taila* in Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India and CCRAS guidelines are Acid value, Specific gravity, Saponification value and Iodine value.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

The initial purpose of the study was to confirm the authenticity of the drugs used in preparation of *Lashunadi Taila*. For this, all ingredients were subjected to organoleptic and microscopic evaluations to confirm the genuineness of all the raw drugs. Later, after the preparation of formulation, pharmacognostical evaluation was carried out. Organoleptic features like colour, odour and taste of *Lashunadi Taila* were recorded and are placed in Table 2.

Table No 2: Organoleptic Characters Of *Lashunadi Taila*.

Parameter	Result
Colour	Yellowish
Odour	Agreeable
Taste	Bitter & Slight Sweet
Touch	Sticky

Microscopic evaluation: Microscopic evaluation was conducted by dissolving the ingredients of *Lashunadi Taila* in the distilled water and was studied under microscope for the presence of characteristics of ingredients of *Lashunadi Taila*. The diagnostic characters of *Lashuna* are Crystalline material (Figure 1 A), and oil globule (Figure 1 B), brown content of

Pippali(Figure 1 C), Cork cells of *Chavya* (Figure 1 D), Stone cells of *Chitraka*(Figure 2 A), Lignified fibres of *Shringavera* (Figure 2 B), Rossette crystals of *Amlavetasa* (Figure 2 C), group of stone cells of *Maricha* (Figure 2 D), Black debris of *Maricha* (Figure 3 A), Prismatic crystal of *Vidari* (Figure 3 B), Acicular crystals of *Shatavari* (Figure 3 C), Cork in surface view of *Ashwagandha*(Figure 3 D), simple unicellular trichome of *Mashaparni* (Figure 4 A), Pitted vessels of *Jivanti*(Figure 4 B), Parenchyma cells with starch grains of *Kapikachchhu* (Figure 4 C), Prismatic crystals of *Atibala* (Figure 4 D), Acicular crystals of *Krishna Musali* (Figure 5 A), stone cells of *Karkatashringi* (Figure 5 B), silixca deposition of *Amalaki*(Figure 5 C), Epicarp cells of *Haritaki*(Figure 5 D), pitted stone cells of *Bilva*(Figure 6 A), Lignified cork of *Patala*(Figure 6 B), Cork cells of *Shyonaka* (Figure 6 C), Simple Trichome of *Shalaparni* (Figure 6 D), spiral vessels of *Prishniparni* (Figure 7 A), Stellate trichome of *Kantakari* (Figure 7 B), Fibres of *Gokshura* (Figure 7 C).

Physico-chemical parameters: Physico-chemical parameters like Acid value, Specific gravity, Saponification value and Iodine value were found within the normal range. Details are shown in Table 3.

Table No 3: Physico-Chemical Parameters Oflashunadi Taila.

S.N.	Parameters	<i>Lashunadi Taila</i>
1	Acid value	12.04
2	Specific gravity	0.91
3	Saponification value	386.46
4	Iodine value	649.13

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

DISCUSSION

The pharmacognostical evaluation of *Lashunadi Taila* was undertaken to establish the authenticity, purity, and quality of the formulation. Organoleptic assessment revealed characteristic features such as yellowish colour, agreeable odour, bitter–slightly sweet taste, and sticky touch, which are consistent with classical descriptions and indicate proper preparation of the *Taila*. These sensory attributes serve as preliminary yet important indicators of genuineness and uniformity of the formulation.

Microscopic examination confirmed the presence of diagnostic characters of all constituent drugs, including crystalline materials, oil globules, stone cells, lignified fibres, trichomes, vessels, and various crystal forms. The observation of these specific microscopic features validates the correct identification of raw materials and supports the integrity of the polyherbal composition. Such findings reinforce the role of pharmacognostical studies in preventing adulteration and ensuring standardization of Ayurvedic formulations.

Physico-chemical parameters such as acid value, specific gravity, saponification value, and iodine value were found to be within the prescribed limits as per Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India and CCRAS guidelines. These results indicate acceptable stability, proper lipid composition, and suitability of the formulation for therapeutic use. Overall, the

pharmacognostical and physico-chemical findings confirm the quality and standardization of *Lashunadi Taila*, supporting its safe and effective application in the management of *Vandhyatva* due to anovulatory factor associated with obesity.

CONCLUSIONS

Pharmacognostical and physico-chemical observations revealed the specific characteristics of all active constituents of *Lashunadi Taila* confirmed the purity and genuineness of the drug.

REFERENCE

1. World Health Organization (WHO) [homepage on the Internet] infertility: WHO 22 May 2024, overview [Retrieved on 18/09/2025] [Available from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/infertility>]
2. American Society for Reproductive Medicine. Age and Fertility (patient education booklet). ReproductiveFacts.org; [cited 2025 Sep 20]. Available from:
3. <https://www.reproductivefacts.org/news-and-publications/fact-sheets-and-nfographics/age-and-fertility-booklet/>
https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK556033/?utm_source
4. World Health Organization (WHO) [homepage on the Internet] 1 in 6 people globally affected by infertility: WHO 4 April 2023, News release, Geneva, Switzerland [Retrieved on 15/09/2025] [Available from: <https://www.who.int/news/item/04-04-2023-1-in-6-people-globally-affected-by-infertility>]
5. Infecundity, infertility, and childlessness in developing countries. DHS Comparative Reports No 9. Calverton, Maryland, USA: ORC Macro and the World Health Organization; 2004. World Health Organization. [Google Scholar] [Retrieved on 15/09/2025] [Available from: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3237240/#ref1>]
6. Vriddha Jivaka, Kashyapa Samhita, Sutra Sthana, 27/19,29, Pandit Hemaraja Sharma Commentator, 6th edition, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Samsthan, Varanasi, 1998; 41,42.
7. The Kashyapa Samhita or Vrdhdhajivakiya Tantra by Vrdhdha Jivaka revised by Vatsya with Sanskrit introduction by Rajaguru Pandit Hemraja Sharma with the Vidyotini Hindi commentary and Hindi translation of Sanskrit introduction by Ayurvedalankar Shri Satyapala Bhashagacharya, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi. Kalpa Sthana, chapter Lashunakalpa, Shloka, 93-95, 271.
8. Wallis TE, Text book of Pharmacognosy, 5th edition, New Delhi: CBS Publisher & amp; Distributors, 2002; 123-132, 210-215.